

In vitro and *in vivo* effects of *Amanita muscaria* tincture on the *a. basilaris* contractility and on a rotenone-induced model of Parkinson's disease

Magdalena Kondeva-Burdina¹, Georgi Popov², Aleksandar Shkondrov³, Boris Kadinov⁴, Vasil Manov², Ilina Krasteva³

1 Laboratory of Drug metabolism and Drug toxicity, Department of Pharmacology, Pharmacotherapy and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Department of Domestic non-communicable disease, Pathology and Pharmacology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Forestry, Sofia, Bulgaria

3 Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Institute of Neurobiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Aleksandar Shkondrov (shkondrov@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 3 February 2026 ♦ Accepted 13 February 2026 ♦ Published 5 March 2026

Citation: Kondeva-Burdina M, Popov G, Shkondrov A, Kadinov B, Manov V, Krasteva I (2026) *In vitro* and *in vivo* effects of *Amanita muscaria* tincture on the *a. basilaris* contractility and on a rotenone-induced model of Parkinson's disease. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e187461>

Abstract

Amanita muscaria is a well-known mushroom containing the GABAA receptor agonist muscimol, a compound of growing interest due to its potential neuroprotective properties. The present study investigated the *in vivo* neuroprotective effects of an *A. muscaria* tincture (AM) in a rotenone-induced mouse model of Parkinson's disease and evaluated its *in vitro* effects on the contractility of rat *arteria basilaris*. Muscimol content in the tincture was quantified by HPLC. Mice were treated with AM alone or in combination with rotenone for 30 days, after which oxidative stress markers and brain histology were assessed. Rotenone significantly increased malondialdehyde levels and lowered reduced glutathione concentrations in brain homogenates, accompanied by marked degenerative-necrotic changes. Co-treatment with AM significantly attenuated lipid peroxidation, preserved glutathione levels, and maintained brain histoarchitectonics. *In vitro* vascular studies demonstrated that both AM and pure muscimol (10 μM) significantly reduced the basal tone of isolated rat *a. basilaris*. These findings demonstrate a pronounced neuroprotective effect of *A. muscaria* tincture in a rotenone-induced model of Parkinsonism and reveal a vasorelaxant action of muscimol on cerebral arteries.

Keywords

Amanita muscaria, *arteria*, contractility, muscimol, Parkinson's disease, rotenone, tremor

Introduction

In recent decades, due to the progressive aging of the population, neurodegenerative diseases have become among the most significant, posing a serious threat to

the quality of human life. With advancing age, a wide range of pathophysiological changes are observed, associated with psychomotor symptoms of varying degrees of manifestation, including memory loss and cognitive impairment (dementia), impaired movements

(tremor), and even disability. In addition to affecting the quality of life of the individual, this group of diseases has a negative impact on the family environment and represents a significant burden on the social and health systems. For this reason, it is extremely important to identify the causes and factors leading to the occurrence of neurodegenerative diseases, to develop effective monitoring models and biomarkers for their monitoring, and, last but not least, successful methods of treatment and prevention (Dauer and Przedborski 2003). Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Huntington's disease (HD), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) are a group of neurodegenerative diseases characterized by diverse etiology, morphology, and pathophysiological symptoms, which ultimately lead to neuronal loss. Studies in the field show that their development is determined by a combination of some or all of the following factors: formation of protein plaques because of an imbalance between the formation and degradation of specific proteins; oxidative stress, accompanied by the formation and accumulation of free radicals; disorders in the processes of energy transfer and mitochondrial dysfunction of neurons; or exposure to heavy metals and pesticides (Dauer and Przedborski 2003).

One of the interesting representatives of the Mushroom kingdom is the well-known red fly agaric, or *Amanita muscaria*. In recent years, this mushroom has attracted the attention of researchers because of its potential antioxidant properties. Since ancient times, it has been better known as one of the most toxic and deadly mushrooms on earth. The main components to which it owes its toxicity are isoxazole derivatives—muskazone, ibotenic acid, and muscarine—with potential neurotoxicity (Scotti de Carolis et al. 1969).

Muscimol has been identified as one of the less toxic biologically active substances responsible for the psychogenic and sedative effects of *A. muscaria* and is a non-selective GABA-A receptor agonist whose levels are not affected by GABA transaminases (aminotransferases). It has been found to have 10 times better affinity for the GABA-A receptor than GABA itself when administered *in vitro* (Scotti de Carolis et al. 1969). Early studies, in which micrograms of muscimol were injected into the globus pallidus before thermal lesioning, showed temporary relief of PD symptoms (Czuczwar et al. 1984). Other studies have shown positive effects on hypoxia-induced amnesia. As a GABA-A receptor agonist, it is of interest to investigate the possible effects of muscimol on the activity of monoamine oxidase (MAO) enzymes, and in particular the MAO-B isoform. There are studies related to its effects in patients diagnosed with Parkinson's disease (Krogsgaard-Larsen 1979).

The aim of the present study was to investigate *in vivo* the possible neuroprotective effects of *Amanita muscaria* tincture (AM), containing mainly muscimol, in a model of rotenone-induced Parkinsonism in mice and to evaluate *in vitro* the effects of the tincture on the contractility of *a. basilaris*.

Materials and methods

Extraction and determination of muscimol

A. muscaria caps were collected in May 2024 in Vitosha Mt., Bulgaria, and identified by Vladimir Vazharov. A voucher specimen was deposited in his personal collection (Vazharov 2016). The material (100 g) was dried at room temperature, cut into pieces, and then left to macerate with 70% ethanol (1:1) for 21 days. The tincture was filtered and used for the experiments. The analysis of the muscimol content was performed following a previously described high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) procedure (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2019). Muscimol content in the tincture was 3.02 ± 0.02 mg/ml.

Experimental animals

The studies were conducted on 18 male white mice, ICR line, with b.w. 15–30 g, and six male white rats, Wistar breed, with b.w. 150–200 g. The animals were obtained from the National Breeding Centre at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Slivnitsa, Bulgaria, and were raised under standard conditions in Plexiglas cages with free access to water and food and a 12 h light/12 h dark regime at a temperature of 20–25 °C. Twelve hours before each specific study, the animals were deprived of food.

Ethical clearance for the experiment was obtained from the Bulgarian Agency of Food Safety (clearance No. 347, valid to 27 March 2028), following the principles stated in the European Directive 2010/63/EU. The experiments were conducted in accordance with Regulation No. 15 on minimum requirements for the protection and humane treatment of experimental animals (SG No. 17, 2006) and the European Regulation for work with experimental animals.

In vivo experiment

Design

Eighteen mice were used for this experiment and were randomly allocated into three experimental groups (n = 6).

Group I—control group of animals treated with saline i.p. (0.5 mL/g).

Group II—animals treated with rotenone (R) (3 mg.kg⁻¹/i.p./30 days) (Salama et al. 2017).

Group III—animals treated simultaneously with rotenone (3 mg.kg⁻¹/i.p./30 days) and AM (muscimol, 2 mg.kg⁻¹/i.p./30 days).

After the end of the experiment, mice were sacrificed by cervical dislocation. The brains were extracted and immediately stored on ice.

Determination of malondialdehyde (MDA) in brain homogenate

The brain homogenate was obtained by homogenizing the brain with potassium–sodium phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4). To the resulting homogenate, 25%

trichloroacetic acid and 0.67% thiobarbituric acid were added. The samples were heated at 100 °C for 20 min and then centrifuged at 4000 × g for 20 min. After cooling, MDA was determined spectrophotometrically at 532 nm (Bai et al. 2007). The MDA concentration was calculated by the molar extinction coefficient of the malondialdehyde–thiobarbituric acid complex and expressed in nmol/g fresh tissue.

Determination of reduced glutathione (GSH) in brain homogenate

The brain was homogenized with 5% trichloroacetic acid. The homogenate was centrifuged at 4000 × g for 20 min. Potassium–sodium phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 8) and Ellman's reagent were added to the supernatant. After cooling, GSH was determined spectrophotometrically at 412 nm (Bai et al. 2007). The GSH concentration was calculated by the molar extinction coefficient and expressed in nmol/g fresh tissue.

Statistical analysis of the results from the in vivo experiment

The results were statistically analyzed using the statistical program MedCalc, applying the non-parametric Mann–Whitney method at significance levels $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$, and $P < 0.001$.

Pathohistological examination

Samples from the brains of the mice were fixed in 10% buffered neutral formalin solution. The fixed materials were dehydrated by passing through an ascending alcohol series—50%, 60%, 70%, 80%, 90%, 96%, and absolute alcohol (in each concentration they were kept for 3 h). After dehydration, the samples were clarified in xylene and embedded in paraffin blocks, which were cut with a rotary microtome at a section thickness of 5 µm. The sections thus prepared were attached to slides using histological glue and processed again with xylene and then dehydrated by passing through a descending alcohol series—absolute alcohol, 96%, 90%, 80%, 70%, 60%, and 50%. After staining with hematoxylin–eosin, microscopic examination and photography were performed with a Levenhuk D740T light microscope with an integrated camera.

Determination of contractile activity of *a. basilaris*

Male sexually mature Wistar rats were killed by stunning, followed by decapitation. The brain was excised within 5 min from the skull of the laboratory animal after sacrifice. Under a binocular loupe, the *a. basilaris*, together with a part of the connective tissue, was carefully dissected, and then the connective tissue was removed using fine scissors and forceps until a clear blood vessel was obtained. The dissected arteries were stored in modified Krebs solution (physiological salt solution (PSS)) for 20 min. The isolated vascular segments of the *a. basilaris* were placed for 20 min in ice-cold modified

Krebs solution. An 18–20 mm long piece of the artery was threaded onto two 40 µm diameter stainless steel wires and mounted on a wire myograph (model 410A, JP Trading, Denmark), containing physiological salt solution consisting of (in mM): 120 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 1.2 NaH₂PO₄, 1 MgSO₄, 1.6 CaCl₂, 0.025 EDTA, 5.5 Glucose, 26 NaHCO₃, and 5 HEPES (pH 7.4). Isometric force was recorded with the program Myodaq (JP Trading, Denmark). In most experiments, the endothelium was intact. Probes for temperature and pH were placed in the experimental chamber, and these parameters were controlled throughout the experiment.

Mounting of the vascular preparations

The arterial vascular segments, after being dissected free from the surrounding tissues (fat and connective), were mounted on two 40 µm thick stainless steel wires in a solution with the same composition as that in which they were isolated. The mounted preparations were attached with steel jaw screws in a controlled-volume organ tray of a wire myograph, containing PSS solution with pH 7.4, which was continuously aerated with carbogen (95% O₂ + 5% CO₂). The absence of CaCl₂ is necessary to ensure a dilated state of the vascular musculature, thus minimizing mechanical trauma to the arterial wall during dissection procedures (Hessellund et al. 2003). One jaw of the myograph was connected to a micrometer that adjusted the distance between the two wires, and the second wire was mounted on a second jaw connected to a piezoelectric strain gauge. Finally, connective tissue and fatty residues around the vessel were carefully removed using fine scissors and tweezers. The procedure for dissecting the arterial preparations and mounting the segments on the apparatus lasted an average of 1 h (Mulvany and Halpern 1977). It was carried out at a temperature of the working solutions of 2–4 °C.

Normalization

Once mounted, the vessel was allowed to equilibrate in the bath for 30 min in a PSS medium of the same composition as the isolation and mounting solution of the preparations and 2.5 mM CaCl₂ at 37 °C with continuous aeration with carbogen. After a 30 min equilibration period, the vessel preparation was normalized to a passive tension equivalent to that required to produce 90% of its diameter (diameter D100) when the vessel is exposed to a transmural pressure of 100 mmHg (Mulvany and Halpern 1977). Essentially, the normalization procedure is as follows: initially, in a completely unloaded state, the preparations were stretched by moving apart the two wires on which the arterial vessel was mounted. Each step of stretching produced an increase in tension. In each condition, the vessels were held for about 100–120 s, during which time the vessels, after a rapid and brief contraction, reached a stable tension level. This process was repeated as many times as necessary to achieve such a stretch of the vessels that would generate a tension value equivalent to 90% of

the passive diameter, and at this diameter the effective pressure is 13.3 kPa (100 mmHg) (Mulvany and Halpern 1977). The normalization procedure takes into account the differences in the length and diameter of the segments, thus allowing the study of different vessels under identical conditions of intravascular pressures that are very close to those in intact biological objects. After normalization, the vessel was incubated for about 30 min before the actual experimental procedure. In each experiment, the vitality of the preparation was tested by successive applications of PSS to re-contract vascular segments at the beginning of the experiment after the normalization procedure.

Incubation of the vessel with the substances

One hour after mounting and 30 min after normalization, the tested substances were incubated with the vessel. AM, or muscimol, was added to the PSS chamber of the wire myograph as a concentrated solution in order to produce a 10 μ M concentration of muscimol when mixed with PSS. Incubation lasted one hour, during which the contractile activity of the arterial segments was recorded.

Statistical processing of the results from contractility

The obtained experimental data were processed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) method. The results are presented as arithmetic mean values obtained from preparations isolated from individual experimental animals. The standard error (\pm SEM) of the arithmetic mean value was also determined. Statistical significance when comparing the mean values was determined by Student's t-test and Tukey–Kramer multiple comparison test for paired and group data at a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$. The computer programs GraphPad InStat v2.04 and v3.02, Origin Pro 7.5 PRO, Corel Draw, and MyoData v2.02 were used for statistical processing of the data, construction of the graphs, and the overall layout of the figures.

Results and discussion

In vivo effect of AM in combination with rotenone on GSH levels and MDA production in brain homogenate

Rotenone alone increased MDA production statistically significantly by 110% and decreased GSH levels by 40%, compared to the control (untreated mice) (Fig. 1).

In combination with rotenone, AM exhibited a statistically significant neuroprotective effect, reducing MDA production by 38%, compared to pure rotenone; it also preserved GSH levels by 42%, compared to the toxic pesticide (Fig. 1). These results were also confirmed by histological studies.

In vivo effect of AM in combination with rotenone on the histology of mice brains

The histological structure of the midbrain and cerebellum of the animals from the different groups was recorded by microscopic examination. In the control group, no microscopically visible damage was found in the ganglion and glial cells of the brain parenchyma (Fig. 2A). In the brain tissue of the animals treated with rotenone, distinct degenerative-necrotic changes were found. Pyknotic changes were observed in some of the ganglion cells, visible from the presence of narrowed, shrunken, dark basophilic nuclei and intensely stained eosinophilic cytoplasm. In some of the neuronal cells, well-defined intracytoplasmic protein deposits were found, forming Lewy bodies (Fig. 2B). Extensive areas with distinct vacuolization of the intercellular space were observed. Pyknotic and lytic changes were found in some Purkinje cells of the cerebellum (Fig. 2C). Microscopic examination of the brains of mice treated with rotenone in combination with AM revealed preserved histoarchitectonics. Alternative changes were single on the background of morphologically unchanged

Figure 1. Effect of *A. muscaria* tincture (AM), in combination with rotenone (R), on GSH levels and MDA production; ** $P < 0.01$ versus control (untreated mice); ++ $P < 0.01$ versus mice treated with rotenone alone.

ganglion and glial cells (Fig. 2D). In separate areas of the brain tissue, glial nodules were formed (Fig. 2E), and active neuronophagy (Fig. 2F) was observed.

Pyknotic changes in the cell nuclei against the background of intensely eosinophilic cytoplasm are indicative of alterations of degenerative-necrotic origin. The presence of distinct protein precipitates in the cell cytoplasm

(Lewy bodies) is a sign of degenerative changes in the brain tissue. The observed glial nodules and active neuronophagy are indicative of previous alternative changes and a regenerative response of the organism, aimed at eliminating the defect. Based on the established histological findings, it can be stated that AM has a pronounced neuroprotective effect in rotenone-induced toxicity,

Figure 2. Histological examination of mouse midbrains (H&E, 400 \times). **A.** Control group of animals: normal histoarchitectonics of the brain tissue; **B.** Animal treated with rotenone: pyknotic changes in the cellular structures and Lewy bodies in the cytoplasm of some ganglion cells (arrow); **C.** Animal treated with rotenone: pyknotic and lytic changes in Purkinje cells; **D.** Animal treated with rotenone and AM: preserved microscopic structure of the brain tissue; **E.** Animal treated with rotenone and AM: glial nodule (arrow) in the brain tissue; **F.** Animal treated with rotenone and AM: active neuronophagy of the alterative zone in the brain tissue.

expressed in the preservation of the microscopic architectonics of the brain tissue and single degenerative-necrotic changes in the cellular structures.

In vitro* evaluation of the effects of AM and pure muscimol on the contractile activity of *a. basilaris

The statistical analysis of the results revealed a decrease in the tension of the vessels treated with AM and muscimol (concentration 10 μ M), compared to the control group (non-treated). Incubation of *a. basilaris* with AM containing a concentration of 10^{-2} mmol/l muscimol statistically significantly reduced vascular tone by 25%, compared to the control (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Effect of AM (as 10 μ M muscimol) on the tension of *a. basilaris*.

Incubation of *a. basilaris* with a solution of pure muscimol, at a concentration of 10^{-2} mmol/l, statistically significantly reduced vascular tone by 30%, compared to the control (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Effect of pure muscimol (10 μ M) on the tension of *a. basilaris*.

The results of the statistical analysis are presented in Fig. 5. They show a statistically significant decrease in vascular tone compared to the control.

Figure 5. Results of the statistical analysis of the tension of vessels treated with AM and pure muscimol, compared to the control.

The findings are in agreement with previous reports on the possible neuroprotective effects of AM in different models of neurotoxicity in rat brain microsomes, mitochondria, and synaptosomes, as well as in the neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2019). The tincture revealed statistically significant neuroprotective effects in the *in vitro* neurotoxicity models and no inhibitory activity on the hMAO-B enzyme. In the present study, the protective effect against rotenone-induced brain injury, with Parkinson's symptoms, was found both biochemically and pathohistologically. Other studies report that AM had no significant effect on the activity of hMAO-B, but pure muscimol did (Voynova et al. 2021). This leads to the conclusion that possible synergism between the components of the tincture and muscimol is present. To date, no data are available on the contractile properties of arteries under muscimol influence. There are reports on the tension properties of the alkaloid on tracheal smooth muscles (Tamaoki et al. 1987) and on ileum smooth muscles (Koutsoviti-Papadopoulou et al. 2003). The observed results are in agreement with these papers. This research provides a basis for further and deeper examination of the pharmacological properties of alcohol extracts of *A. muscaria*.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that *Amanita muscaria* tincture, containing predominantly muscimol, exerts a significant neuroprotective effect in a rotenone-induced model of Parkinson's disease. The protective action is evidenced by attenuation of oxidative stress, preservation of brain histoarchitectonics, and reduction of degenerative-necrotic alterations. In addition, both the tincture and pure muscimol reduced the basal tone of isolated rat *arteria basilaris*, revealing a previously unreported

vasorelaxant effect on cerebral vessels. These findings suggest possible synergism among constituents of the tincture and provide a rationale for further investigation of *A. muscaria*-derived preparations as neuroprotective and cerebrovascular modulators.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: № 347/valid to 27.03.2028.

References

- Bai X, Qiu A, Guan J, Shi Z (2007) Antioxidant and protective effect of an oleanolic acid-enriched extract of *A. deliciosa* root on carbon tetrachloride induced rat liver injury. *Asia Pacific journal of clinical nutrition* 16 [Suppl 1]: 169–173.
- Czuczwar SJ, Chmielewska B, Turski WA, Kleinrok Z (1984) Differential effects of baclofen, gamma-hydroxybutyric acid and muscimol on the protective action of phenobarbital and diphenylhydantoin against maximal electroshock-induced seizures in mice. *Neuropharmacology* 23: 159–163. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0028-3908\(84\)80008-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0028-3908(84)80008-8)
- Dauer W, Przedborski S (2003) Parkinson's disease: mechanisms and models. *Neuron* 39: 889–909. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0896-6273\(03\)00568-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0896-6273(03)00568-3)
- Hessellund A, Jeppesen P, Aalkjaer C, Bek T (2003) Characterization of vasomotion in porcine retinal arterioles. *Acta ophthalmologica Scandinavica* 81: 278–282. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0420.2003.00063.x>
- Kondeva-Burdina M, Voynova M, Shkondrov A, Aluani D, Tzankova V, Krasteva I (2019) Effects of *Amanita muscaria* extract on different *in vitro* neurotoxicity models at sub-cellular and cellular levels. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 132: 110687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2019.110687>
- Koutsoviti-Papadopoulou M, Nikolaidis E, Kounenis G (2003) Enhancing and inhibitory effects of H₂-receptor antagonists on the GABA and the GABAA-agonist muscimol responses of the isolated guinea pig ileum: a pharmacodynamic interaction. *Pharmacological Research* 48(3): 279–284. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1043-6618\(03\)00148-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1043-6618(03)00148-8)
- Krogsgaard-Larsen P (1979) GABA-neurotransmitters pharmacological, biochemical and pharmacological aspects GABA-neurotransmitters: pharmacological, biochemical and pharmacological aspects. Munksgaard, Copenhagen.
- Mulvany MJ, Halpern W (1977) Contractile properties of small arterial resistance vessels in spontaneously hypertensive and normotensive rats. *Circulation research* 41: 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.res.41.1.19>
- Salama M, Sobh M, Emam M, Abdalla A, Sabry D, El-Gamal M, Lotfy A, El-Husseiny M, Sobh M, Shalash A, Mohamed WM (2017) Effect of intranasal stem cell administration on the nigrostriatal system in a mouse model of Parkinson's disease. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine* 13: 976–982. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2017.4073>
- Scotti de Carolis A, Lippardini F, Longo VG (1969) Neuropharmacological investigations on muscimol, a psychotropic drug extracted from *Amanita muscaria*. *Psychopharmacologia* 15: 186–195. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00411168>
- Tamaoki J, Graf PD, Nadel JA (1987) Effect of gamma-aminobutyric acid on neurally mediated contraction of guinea pig trachealis smooth muscle. *The Journal of pharmacology and experimental therapeutics* 243: 86–90. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3565\(25\)39257-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3565(25)39257-8)
- Vazharov V (2016) Medicinal fungi in Bulgaria. Biana, Sofia.
- Voynova M, Shkondrov A, Krasteva I, Kondeva-Burdina M (2021) *In vitro* effects of synthetic muscimol and an extract from *Amanita muscaria* on human recombinant MAOB enzyme. *Pharmacia* 68: 147–150. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.68.e60705.figure1>

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study is financed by the European Union—NextGenerationEU through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No. BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Aleksandar Shkondrov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5091-6058>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.